

SYNTHESIS AND REACTIONS OF α -BROMO- α -*iso*NITROSOACETONE,
 α -BROMO- α' -*iso*NITROSOACETONE, α -BROMO- α -NITROSODIETHYL,
KETONE AND α -BROMO- α' -*iso*NITROSODIETHYL, KETONE

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Synthesis, characterisation and reactions of α -bromo- α -*isonitrosoacetone*, α -bromo- α' -*isonitrosoacetone*, α -bromo- α -nitrosodiethyl ketone and α -bromo- α' -*isonitrosodiethyl ketone* have been described.

In an earlier communication (Singhal and Bokadia, this *issue*, p. 893) synthesis and reactions of α -bromo- α -*isonitrosoacetophenone* and α -bromo- α -*isonitroso*- (*p*-methoxy-, *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromo-)acetophenones have been described. In the present investigation two lines of attack have been followed to obtain the bromo*isonitroso* ketones: (i) to prepare the free *isonitroso* ketones and then to brominate them either in the free form or in the form of metallic salts, and (ii) to prepare the bromo*ketones* and then subject them to the process of nitrosation by the action of alkyl nitrite in the presence of hydrogen chloride. The first method has been successfully applied in the synthesis of bromoformyl ketones by several workers (Brühl, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2175; Wislicenus and Ruthing, *Annalen.*, 1912, 379, 260; Deshapande *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 43; 1949, 26, 55; Garg, Singh and Bokadia, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 353; Garg and Bokadia, *ibid.*, 1957, 34, 286). Formylation of bromo*ketones* has not been successful in yielding bromo-oxymethylene ketones. In an attempt to prepare α -formyl- α -bromoacetophenone, Pathak, Singhal and Bokadia (*J. Vh. Univ.*, 1958, 2, 160) obtained *sym.*-tribenzoylcyclopropane as the sole product of the reaction (cf. Paul and Schulze, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 2425; Campbell and Khanna, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, suppl. issue, No. I S 33-36; Garg, Garg and Bokadia, *Agra Univ. J. Res.*, 1957, 6, 19). But Bokadia, Singhal and Pathak (*loc. cit.*) have, however, successfully prepared formyl compounds from halogen esters.

Piloty *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 3093) brominated oximes in pyridine. Chloro-*isonitroso* ketones have been synthesised by the nitroso-chlorination of ketones (Rheinboldt and Dumont, *Annalen*, 1925, 545, 125, 118; *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 327). Levin and Hartung (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, 7, 408) prepared ω -chloro*isonitrosoacetophenone* by the action of RONO (alkyl nitrite) on ω -chloroacetophenone in the presence of hydrogen chloride. Ponzio and Charrier (*Gazzetta*, 1907, 37, 101) and Steinkopf, Miege and Herold (*Ber.*, 1920, 53, 1147) synthesised α -bromo- α -*isonitrosoacetone* by the action of fuming nitric acid on acetone, followed by treatment with hydrogen bromide.

In the present investigation free *isonitroso* ketones and their copper salts have been brominated under different conditions.

When bromoacetone and bromodiethyl ketones were treated with RONO (R=alkyl) in the presence of hydrogen chloride, they yielded the isomeric α -bromo- α' -*isonitroso* compounds (I), as proved by oxidative fission.

All the above four compounds are colorless crystalline solids and reduce Fehling's solution. α -Bromo- α -isonitrosoacetone, α -bromo- α' -isonitrosoacetone and α -bromo- α' -isonitrosodiethyl ketone develop a wine-red colour with pyridine; the first two ketones develop a violet colour with ferric chloride solution. α -Bromo- α' -isonitrosoacetone, α -bromo- α -nitrosodiethyl ketone and α -bromo- α' -isonitrosodiethyl ketone liberate iodine on being warmed with acidified potassium iodide solution. But α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetone does not oxidise potassium iodide solution. It seems that a bromine atom attached to a carbon atom containing isonitroso group has got no oxidising property, while a bromine atom attached to a nitroso carbon atom has got oxidising tendency.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of α -Bromo- α -isonitrosoacetone: Method I.—To an aqueous solution of isonitrosoacetone (10 g.) a saturated solution of copper acetate was added gradually. The precipitated copper salt was kept overnight at 0° and then it was filtered and purified by repeated washing with petroleum ether. The purified salt is soluble in benzene and sparingly soluble in water. It melts at 190° (decomp.). (Found: Cu, 25.2. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cu}$ requires Cu, 26.9%). The copper complex (12 g.) was suspended in dry ether, cooled and a solution of bromine (15.9 g.) was added to it and left overnight. It was washed twice with water and dried. On evaporation it gave a solid mass which was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 123° , yield 3 g. (Found: Br, 48.9. Calc. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NBr}$: Br, 48.1%).

Method II.—Free isonitrosoacetone (8.7 g.) was taken in a three-necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer and purified pyridine (6 g.), benzene (10 c.c.) and ether (25 c.c.) were added to it. The mixture was well cooled and bromine (15 g.) was added to it gradually with constant shaking, and allowed to stand for 6 hours to complete the reaction. The mixture was then twice washed with water, dried over fused calcium chloride and evaporated. A gummy product was obtained by petroleum ether. It was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 123° , yield 3.2 g.

α -Bromo- α -isonitrosoacetone is a colorless crystalline solid, soluble in water, benzene, ether, petroleum ether and carbon tetrachloride. It is a very strong lachrymator in solution form.

Synthesis of α -Bromo- α' -isonitrosoacetone.—Bromoacetone (65 g.) and dry ether (100 c.c.) were taken in the reaction flask. The stirrer was started and after the liquid had become homogeneous, a current of dry hydrogen chloride was passed. To this mixture isopropyl nitrite (42.2 g.) was added in several small instalments. After addition of the first instalment, the reaction mixture became orange-brown

and after several minutes, light yellow. At this stage the next instalment was added. At the last instalment the reaction was very vigorous. After completion of addition it was left overnight. From the reaction mixture ether was removed on a water-bath and the unchanged isopropyl nitrite and isopropyl alcohol were removed under reduced pressure. The residue on evaporation gave a solid mass which was repeatedly crystallised from CCl_4 , m.p. $89-90^\circ$, yield 20 g. (Found: C, 19.4; H, 1.87; N, 7.04; Br, 48.1. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{NBr}$ requires C, 21.6; H, 2.4; N, 8.4; Br, 48.1%).

α -Bromo- α' -isonitrosoacetone is a colorless, white, shining solid, soluble in water, benzene, ether and alcohol, and sparingly soluble in CCl_4 . Its solution in benzene is a strong lachrymator.

The bromo compound (2 g.) was treated with a mixture of potassium dichromate (5.5 g.), H_2SO_4 (conc., 4 c.c.) and water (25 c.c.) and left for 24 hours at room temperature and then washed with 2 c.c. of water. The ethereal extract after evaporation of the solvent gave the bromo-acetic acid, m.p. 48° (lit. m.p. 50°), equiv., 137.1 (calc. 139).

Synthesis of α -Bromo- α -nitrosodiethyl Ketone: Method I.—Bromination of copper complex (m.p. 145° . Found: Cu, 20.1. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cu}$ requires Cu, 21.7%) was effected in the same manner as in the case of α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetone. The solid product on crystallisation from CCl_4 melted at 85° , yield 1.9 g. (Found: C, 31.15; H, 4.26; N, 7.7; Br, 42.7. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NBr}$ requires C, 30.9; H, 4.1; N, 6.2; Br, 41.9%).

Method II.—Bromination of nitrosodiethyl ketone (5 g.) was carried out in the same manner as described in the case of α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetone. The solid product so obtained was crystallised from CCl_4 , m.p. 85° , yield 1.2 g.

α -Bromo- α -nitrosodiethyl ketone is a white needle-shaped solid, soluble in CCl_4 , ether, benzene and petroleum ether and develops a yellow colour with pyridine. The solution in benzene has got a strong irritating effect.

Synthesis of α -Bromo- α' -isonitrosodiethyl Ketone.—Nitrosation of bromodiethyl ketone (15 g., b.p. $133-34^\circ$) was done in the same manner as described in the case of α -bromo- α' -isonitrosoacetone. It was crystallised from CCl_4 , m.p. 81° , yield 11 g. (Found: C, 31.9; H, 3.97; N, 7.07; Br, 41.9. $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NBr}$ requires C, 30.9; H, 4.1; N, 6.2; Br, 41.2%).

It is a white solid with needle-shaped crystals, soluble in benzene, ether and insoluble in water. It does not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution, but on standing it develops a dark yellow colour. Its solution in benzene is a strong lachrymator. On oxidation with $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7-\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ it gave α -bromopropionic acid, b.p. 200° (lit. b.p. 205°), equiv., 155.6 (calc. 153).

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